

BLOGGERS IN ONLINE MEDIA OF THE DECISION TO TRAVEL IN THAILAND

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ABSTRACT : This paper aimed to study 1) Bloggers in online media of the decision to travel in Thailand With the quantitative method, the questionnaire covered 400 samples of tourist with non-probability and accidental sampling. Then, the data were analyzed with descriptive statistics for the respondent's information and with the correlation and multiple regression to find out any concordances between the bloggers and the decision to travel in Thailand. The research indicated that 1) for the whole of the bloggers, Personal (X_1) ($\beta = 0.412$, $\alpha < .01$) and Photograph (X_4) ($\beta = 0.512$, $\alpha < .05$) had the decision to travel in Thailand. a statistically significant effect on the travel in Thailand.

KEYWORDS - bloggers; online media; decision.

I. INTRODUCTION

Thailand is a country with tourism potential rich in natural resources and Rich culture and traditions Moreover, the tourism industry is one of the important industries in Thailand. In driving the top economy that made a lot of income for the country in 2016 2019 has tourists More than 39.7 million people traveled to Thailand, generating more than 1.93 trillion baht in income [1] It is also relevant to a variety of businesses. Both direct and indirect types Causing the distribution of circular income to various businesses, helping to stimulate Economic expansion and investment in other businesses. Examples of businesses that are directly related are the business of Transportation, hotel and accommodation business, restaurant business and tourism management business And tourism management business Related businesses Indirectly including agricultural products Local handicrafts, clothing, accessories And souvenirs etc.

Planning a trip is the starting point of the trip. From a survey of Hotels.com [2] It was found that Thai tourists attach great importance to travel planning. Review at Related to tourism and opinions from other travelers is what tourists are interested in. It takes up to 95 per cent to decide where to go on an average Thai tourist spends 10 hours. In finding information, that is, tourism planning is the driving force for travel decision making.

Today's world is a world of borderless communication; with technology and the Internet able to make People living in different corners of the world can comfortably communicate with each other. Including sending data, images, sound, various files, including Video calling allows people who are talking to each other to see each other as if they were talking in person, making it more convenient and comfortable. Cost savings which at present has made great progress because there is access to the online networking has become easier and cheaper, making social media more affordable. Influence on use Daily life can be regarded as one of the main factors in sustaining life, which has an impact. On shopping behavior as well Because social media is easily accessible to consumers and Less investment. [3] To communicate through social media Through social tools For use in communicating with each other Through your online channel connected to the Internet In which both the sender and the receiver must be involved with each other. [4]

So, influencers on social media In other words, blogger took over. Very much in the matter of helping spread news or information Because it is a person who has a group of followers Get attention and trust Where

these followers are open to receive news from bloggers by To see that there are some agencies or organizations Including brands and services using bloggers These are in order to get involved in activities that are held by themselves or the organization. With the aim of wanting Information became ubiquitous and gave rise to word of mouth. Which can be called as promoting or doing advertising in another format Therefore, blogger can be compared as another medium for it spreads the news quickly and also has a clear reach to the target audience. [5]

As a result, to study bloggers in online media of the decision to travel in Thailand. To be a guideline for the development of cooperation in the tourism industry for hotel business operators and to build confidence in foreign tourists. This could enable economic recovery in the service industry to return to normal and rapid growth.

II. OBJECTIVES/RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The objectives of this research article were to study bloggers in online media of the decision to travel in Thailand.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The framework of this quantitative research is based on related concepts and theories to study bloggers in online media of the decision to travel in Thailand. with details as follows.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework of this study

Research Methodology

Population and sample group

The population was tourist in Thailand. The sample group consisted of 400 respondents by non-probability sampling and accidental sampling. The number was obtained by calculating the formula without the population at a 95% confidence level, and the sample size was set as follows

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{E^2}$$

Where:

n = Size of the sample group

Z = Reliability level

P = Proportion of the population

E = Highest error value which will happen

The acceptance level was in accordance with the statistical significance level at 0.5

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2(0.5)(1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2}$$
$$= 384.16$$

The sample size was 385 respondents. However, 400 questionnaires were gathered by using a probabilistic sampling method between June - December 2020.

Research Instrument

The research tool was a questionnaire where the samples were asked individually to provide information about Bloggers in online media of the decision to travel in Thailand. The content consisted of 3 parts as follows.

Part 1: General information of the respondents, namely gender, age.

Part 2: Information on factors used in the analysis of Bloggers in online media

Part 3: Information on the concordance between the decision of results to the to travel in Thailand.

Data analyses

The data were collected by distributing questionnaires in the form of filling in information online to provide convenience and speed to comply with the situation of the COVID-19 outbreak.

The quantitative data were analyzed with descriptive statistics for the concordance between the Bloggers in online media of the decision to travel in Thailand by analyzing the correlation coefficient and stepwise multiple regression.

IV. RESULTS

Regarding general data of the respondents, the following were found:

For the general information of the respondents, it was found that 300 respondents, 80%, were female, and 100, 20%, were male. 187 respondents were between 51-60 years old, 43.50%. 137 of them were 41 - 50 years, 18.50%. There were 35 respondents aged 31-40 years, 17.50%, and were 28 respondents aged 30-21 years, 14%. For the age 61 and over, there were 13 respondents, 6.50%.

Factors for analysis of Bloggers in online media of the decision to travel in Thailand

The results of the analysis of Bloggers in online media of the decision to travel in Thailand as a whole were Personal (X_1) ($\beta = 0.412$, $\alpha < .01$) and Photograph (X_4) ($\beta = 0.512$, $\alpha < .05$) had the decision to travel in Thailand. a statistically significant effect on the travel in Thailand. by 52.5% ($R^2 = 0.525$) and the forecasting equations for the bloggers in online media of the decision to travel in Thailand. on the whole (Y) in standardized form was $Z_y = 0.412ZX_1 + 0.512ZX_4$

V. DISCUSSIONS

The results of the analysis of Bloggers in online media of the decision to travel in Thailand as a whole were Personal (X_1) ($\beta = 0.412$, $\alpha < .01$) and Photograph (X_4) ($\beta = 0.512$, $\alpha < .05$) had the decision to travel in Thailand. a statistically significant effect on the travel in Thailand. by 52.5% ($R^2 = 0.525$) and the forecasting equations for the bloggers in online media of the decision to travel in Thailand. on the whole (Y) in standardized form was $Z_y = 0.412ZX_1 + 0.512ZX_4$ [6] Networking in social media as a free travel style Case study I Roam Alone found that the sample Who are interested in the contents of the substance that has been read will be shown Interest or not interested from clicking the Like (Like) button, press Share (Share) or commenting on the content. Have read (Comment) in addition, it is Inviting friends to discuss issues or content that they have read With people who have similar opinions without They must have known each other before. In addition, sharing or sharing Posting content or issues of interest also expands the online community, which creates a network. Independent travel online to be more efficient and sustainable. It also corresponds to [7] Beauty Marketing Blogger on social media "found that the content Using symbols to communicate Emotional or the use of video, images and music for communication in the content will result in More credibility to the content. [8] Do a study on Social media thought influencer communication strategies that influence group attitudes Followers found that a follower's social media usage showed media exposure behavior from Main personal interest Most of the time, content is more images and articles than video clips. This is because photos will create more attraction and interest. With blogger still This allows social media users or followers to feel close to that which they are connected to. This creates trust and Trust in bloggers As a result, bloggers have an influence on their decision to buy a product or service. [9] By promoting through the virtual image is valuable. The greatest influence on planning behavior in travel decisions was followed by public relations. Influential people in tourism And publicity through celebrities, respectively

III. CONCLUSION

A bloggers is content or information produced by a knowledgeable blogger. Aptitude or have Interested in blog content, where in-depth information about products or services is provided by followers Able to enter and comment on the content of the said matter You can also search for information. Various can be found on the internet In the blog, a message of interactions between blogger and Followers Because in today's society it is Of news society Through social media and have a great influence on the decisions or behavior of Followers, which, at the same time, their purchasing decisions are not based on information that is written by The only blogger But the followers have considered the information News for other followers to enter Let's communicate, exchange information and opinions on blogs as well. By blogging that has gained high popularity Tends to have the power to persuade This allows or persuades readers to follow until they make bloggers an influencer. To people who follow or open to news, which will affect the attitudes, perceptions, as well as the behavior of the recipient. In today's world, blogs arise in abundance with content that the blog owner is interested in whether It will be a blog about food, attractions, technology, or beauty. [10] Popular reviews are often from influential reviewers on social media. Influencer is A group of people who like to write stories, stories, experiences that are The expertise was interesting. These people tend to have the ability to influence. Or make other people happen Trust and follow the idea until the following readers are interested in products and services and may lead to Buying decisions can be divided into two main groups: 1) Macro Influencer group is the group with the highest 100,000+ social media followers and 2) Micro Influencer groups are the top 5,000 - 100,000 followers, in conclusion, you can notice that the influencers will be able to reach a group of people. More than reviewers That is a regular tourist, but a regular tourist can give more credibility Influencer. [11]

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